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Citation

Ines Wenger, Helen Lynch, Maria Prellwitz, Christina Schulze. Children's perceptions of factors enhancing play value and inclusion on outdoor playgrounds: a synthesis of qualitative evidence. PROSPERO 2021 CRD42021268705 Available from:

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Review question

How do children with diverse needs experience environmental aspects on outdoor playgrounds in relation to play value and inclusion from a universal design perspective?

Searches

The search strategy has been developed in consultation with a librarian from Zurich University of Applied Sciences in July 2021.

A systematic search of the databases Scopus, AMED, CINAHL, Emcare, MEDLINE, Web of Science, Google Scholar, PsycINFO, ERIC, Avery Index to Architectural Periodicals, RSWBplus, and WTI is planned to be conducted in August and September 2021.

Databases will be searched up to the date of 14.09.2021.

Only peer-reviewed publications in English will be included, as this is the common language in the review team.

The searches will be re-run just before the final analyses.

Unpublished studies will be sought in grey literature databases.

Types of study to be included

This review will consider qualitative studies that draw on the experiences of children regarding play on outdoor playgrounds including, but not limited to, designs such as phenomenology, grounded theory, ethnography, action research and feminist research. Mixed-methods studies will also be included in the review. The studies must report the perspectives of children.

Condition or domain being studied

Play is important for children's well-being and is thus related to children's health (Cole-Hamilton et al., 2002). Playgrounds are understood as outdoor spaces offering specific play equipment for children to play (Burke 2013). For this review studies are included that include playgrounds that are accessible to the public, e.g. in public parks, schools or preeschools (Burke 2013), as well as private playgrounds, e.g. in schools. Play value describes the variety in which an environment or playground equipment can be used. Play value is also created if the environment and playground equipment allow children to be creatively and imaginatively integrated in their play activities (Yuen 2016).

Inclusion is understood as the right of children with and without disabilities to actively take part in community life (UNICEF UK 1989). Universal Design is one way to enhance the inclusion and participation of all people in community life (Steinfeld and Maisel, 2012). Universal Design aims to design products or environments for all people, rather than to provide special adaptations for a few people (Connell et al. 1997). It is

underpinned by the seven principles of universal design developed by Ronald Mace and colleagues in 1997.

Participants/population

Studies investigating the perspectives of children with diverse needs, for example children with and without disabilities, various socio-economic and ethnic backgrounds, and different gender, on playing on playgrounds will be included. Children from birth aged up to 18 years will be included.

Studies applying a mixed-methods design, which allows to clearly extract the children's perspective will also be included. As well as studies that combine different perspectives, such as for example parents or teachers perspective, but allow to identify the perspectives of the children.

Studies investigating only other perspectives than children's perspectives, such as perspectives from parents, teachers etc. will be excluded. Also, studies on children's perspectives on other activities not related to outdoor play will also be excluded.

Intervention(s), exposure(s)

Studies will be included if they explore children's perspective on outdoor play settings on built playgrounds (including natural elements), such as playgrounds in public spaces, parks and schools.

Studies will be excluded if they investigate indoor play settings or other outdoor play settings than built playgrounds, such as parks without a playground setting.

Comparator(s)/control

Not applicable

Context

Outdoor playgrounds on different settings, such as schools, parks, community etc. will be considered.

Main outcome(s)

A synthesis of factors that enhance play value from the perspective of children could help to inform the design of outdoor play settings regarding inclusion, universal design and natural elements.

Measures of effect

Not applicable

Additional outcome(s)

Additional outcomes may be related to factors enhancing play from the perspective of children with disabilities, or in relation to socio-economic and ethnic backgrounds or gender.

Measures of effect

Not applicable

Data extraction (selection and coding)

Studies will be imported in the COVIDENCE extraction tool. As a first step duplicates will be removed. Secondly, two reviewers will independently screen titles and abstracts of the imported studies against inclusion and exclusion criteria. If there is a disagreement among the two reviewers, a third reviewer will be consulted for decision-making. Regular meetings will be held in the review team during the process of study review.

For missing data study investigators will be contacted.

The data extracted will include specific details about the populations (e.g. age range, children with disabilities, ethnic background, socio-economic background, aspects of gender), context (playground setting), culture and geographical location, study methods and the phenomena of interest (e.g. play value, inclusion, environmental factors, principles of universal design) relevant to the review question and specific objectives.

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

The included studies will be critically appraised with the standard Joanna Briggs Institute critical appraisal instrument by two independent reviewers. If the two independent reviewers disagree on a study, the two reviewers will discuss their disagreements. If no agreement can be reached through the discussions, a third independent reviewer will be consulted.

Before starting the review, a cut-off score for the exclusion of studies is set. The cut-off score is determined based on discussions within the entire review team. It is planned to only include the studies that achieve the cut-off score or higher in the review. However, if the amount of identified studies is very small, then studies below the cut-off score might need to be included as well.

Strategy for data synthesis

The data will be synthesized according to thematic synthesis described by Thomas and Harden (2008). In a first step the text, including the results parts of the studies (text and quotations) will be coded 'line-by-line'. The text will be imported into Atlas.ti – a software for qualitative data analysis. In a second step 'descriptive themes' will be developed from the initial coding. In a third step 'analytical themes' will be developed, which should add interpretations or explanations to the findings of the included studies.

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

If the identified studies allow an investigation of subgroups, the data is analysed with regard to the following sub-groups:

Children with disabilities, children with different socio-economic backgrounds, children with different ethnic backgrounds and gender aspects.

These sub-group analysis are done to see if the children's experience of environmental factors, play value or inclusion in relation to outdoor play differs among the sub-groups.

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Type and method of review

Synthesis of qualitative studies, Systematic review

Anticipated or actual start date

27 July 2021

Anticipated completion date

31 July 2022

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Grant number(s)

State the funder, grant or award number and the date of award

Grant number: 861257

Date of award: 01.03.2020

Conflicts of interest

Language

English

Country

Ireland, Sweden, Switzerland

Stage of review

Review Ongoing

Subject index terms status

Subject indexing assigned by CRD

Subject index terms

MeSH headings have not been applied to this record

Date of registration in PROSPERO

29 August 2021

Date of first submission

29 July 2021

Stage of review at time of this submission

The review has not started

Stage	Started	Completed
Preliminary searches	No	No
Piloting of the study selection process	No	No
Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria	No	No
Data extraction	No	No
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	No	No
Data analysis	No	No

The record owner confirms that the information they have supplied for this submission is accurate and complete and they understand that deliberate provision of inaccurate information or omission of data may be construed as scientific misconduct.

The record owner confirms that they will update the status of the review when it is completed and will add publication details in due course.

Versions

29 August 2021

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